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Senior High School Learners' Reading Comprehension Level on Select Subtitled Movies

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Abstract

The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 – R.A. No. 10533 (K to 12 Program) English Curriculum Guide 2013 noted that “the country aims for graduates who are communicatively competent and multi-literate and which learners have learned both meaning and accuracy of macro skills with the strategies and activities catered by the teachers. Gabinete emphasizes that English teachers should prioritize not only reading skills but also incorporate listening, speaking, viewing, and writing abilities in various aspects of curriculum planning, material preparation, assessment, integration, and individualized learning. In this study, the researcher employed quantitative-correlation research with a pre-test and post-test- design to identify the reading comprehension level of Senior High School learners adapted to Barrett’s Taxonomy of Reading Comprehension with subcomponents such as literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation, and appreciation; to determine the significant Relationship in the reading comprehension levels of Senior High School learners in reading subtitles of selected movie; and proposed an informational material in the classification of the reading comprehension levels of Senior High School learners in reading subtitles of selected movies. The participants of this study were the Senior High School learners who were purposively chosen. The study utilized a researcher-made pre-test and post-test instrument that was validated and pilot-tested. Data were gathered personally after the movie with subtitles was played. Data were treated using SPSS for the normality test and Spearman’s rho non-parametric test. Findings revealed that in reading movie subtitles, the comprehension levels of the Senior High School learners in the subcomponents attained a qualitative index of outstanding, and there is no relationship between the subcomponents of comprehension. In line with the findings, Informational Material was developed and recommended in classifying the comprehension levels of Senior High School learners in reading subtitles of the selected movie. Based on the findings and the conclusions of the study, the following are recommended: (1) the movie subtitles may be used to attain outstanding comprehension performance levels of the learners along any of the literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation, and appreciation comprehension; (2) the movies used in classes may be selected with high-quality content and visual characteristics, with quality subtitles, and relevant to the topic; (3) activities may vary for formative and summative assessment adhering to Barrett’s Taxonomy of Reading Comprehension; (4) for the teachers to use movie subtitles, share experiences, research in reading as a macro skill, and create specific guidelines in using movie or video subtitles in lesson plans from motivation to assessments; (5) for the school heads and curriculum or instructional developers to create local policies in using and developing movies or videos with subtitles along specific topics in various subjects, not only in English.

Keywords: *movie subtitles, reading comprehension levels, taxonomy of reading, informational material*

Introduction

Reading from movie subtitles requires a person to construct meaning by interpreting the parts such as images, symbols, conventions, and the text that are significantly related to the message of the text, which is an interaction of sounds, graphics, animations, and design text features that broadly refer to cultural artifacts such as songs, posters, paintings, rituals, and more even the routine practices in the classes that are all interpreted (Saskatchewan et al., 2013) similar to viewing. Viewing has been one of the most effective skills in communication since it is a method of recording information, emphasizing the importance of mental faculties that allow a perceiver to provide facts about a target that is impossible to obtain via conventional senses owing to time, distance, or shielding. Viewing also entails comprehending pictures for which words stand in films, computer programs, and websites and integrating visual imagery with printed or spoken words.

The majority of texts young people are encountering and creating nowadays are multimodal, where the meaning is communicated by multiple modes, like digital multimodal text, which most classroom teachers teach since the focus is given to reading and other skills (Donaghy, 2020). Similarly, the fact that communication nowadays is mainly multimodal changes the construct of communicative competence. It has vast implications for our educational systems, which are presumed to be needed in curriculum content and approach review and revision since viewing as a 21st-century skill is taken less seriously in several countries in the United States and Asia.

The Philippines has been a target for Filipino educators to build up the macro-skills in English for their learners. For this reason, educators do not focus only on the learners' listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills but also on their viewing since these enhance both their reading and listening skills. As learners view visual messages, they need to use a range of viewing and strategies to make sense of the visual images and accompanying oral and print language. However, Carolino and Queroda (2018) noted that teachers must still be fully equipped with instructional strategies and materials to teach learners viewing skills as macro-skills.

About the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 – R.A. No. 10533 (K-12 Program) – K to 12 English Curriculum Guide 2013, it is noted that the country aims for graduates who are communicatively competent and multi-literate and which learners have learned both

meaning and accuracy of macro skills with the strategies and activities catered by the teachers. It was supported further by DepEd Order no. 42, s. 2016 - "Policy Guidelines on Daily Lesson Preparation for the K to 12 Education Program", stating that teachers are given the right to choose strategies and contents for achieving the curriculum objectives whose competencies are not negotiable, but the means for attaining vary depending on the teachers' discretion of what best fits the learners. With this, teachers must teach viewing and relevant skills and subskills with the teacher-crafted classroom curriculum.

Relevant to this, instructional materials like electronic sources are beginning to replace traditional methods with movies and videos. Instructional materials today, like videos with movie subtitles, become interactive, enabling us to respond to the contents, yet complicated in their formats and designs that become hindrances in processing and understanding the contents. This situation of reading with video subtitles calls for an urgent pedagogical and information response from the English teacher in teaching reading because reading from movies in electronic sources has several peculiarities that traditional reading with non-moving backgrounds strategies do not consider. This problem context brought low learner assessment results in reading-related activities and reading.

Additionally, Gabinete (2017) highlighted in a study that teachers' beliefs and practices show that teachers cannot teach and assess visual literacy or viewing skills, which include some reasons such as coping with learners' attitudes, lack of time to prepare the materials, lack of strategy and willingness for expanded literacy notion whereas, appreciation and criticisms are rarely practiced.

In connection with this trend, to help bridge the problem in teaching reading with the viewing material (with subtitles) while motivating learners to learn, facilitators of the teaching and learning process resort to using different electronic materials and even internet resources or platforms in instruction. No informational materials explicitly address the need for reading and viewing simultaneously. Moreover, in English classes, teachers should not focus only on the selected macro skills such as speaking, listening, reading and writing of the learners but also on their viewing relevant to reading skills in the curriculum planning, material preparation and assessment, integration, and individualization of learning for improved comprehension and connections in what is being read and viewed as a literacy (Corpus-Bullecer, 2017).

Lastly, planning to teach for comprehension would be more successful if the learners' comprehension styles were identified (Guieb & Ortega-Dela Cruz, 2017). The study similarly found that only some teaching techniques suit the learners' interests and learning abilities. Furthermore, using technology combined with reading and viewing techniques for comprehension strategies would help academic success and higher learner achievement.

This study aimed to identify the reading comprehension level of Senior High School Learners to fill in the research gap on how movie subtitles impact reading comprehension and its classification. In this study, the use of movies with subtitles was explored apart from using only video clips or movies without subtitles in the class.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the reading comprehension level of Senior High School learners in reading subtitles on selected movies in a public Senior High School. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the reading comprehension level of the Senior High School learners after using movie subtitles in public high school in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. literal comprehension;
 - 1.2. reorganization comprehension;
 - 1.3. inferential comprehension;
 - 1.4. evaluation comprehension, and
 - 1.5. appreciation comprehension?
2. Is there a significant relationship in the comprehension level of Senior High School learners after reading movie subtitles?
3. What is the classification of the comprehension level of Senior High School learners in reading subtitles on selected movies?
4. What informational material can be developed for Senior High School learners' reading comprehension level on subtitles in selected movies?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational study design to identify the reading comprehension of the subtitles in movies level of Senior High School learners in a public High School in Quezon Province which is deemed fit in this study. According to Christensen (2014), this design examines the strength and direction of relationships between variables without manipulating them. Researchers collect data on different variables of interest and analyze them to determine if there is a correlation between the variables of reading comprehension in this study. This type of study design is proper when researchers want to understand the nature of relationships, make predictions, or identify patterns in data that make it fit in this study by conducting post-tests and identifying senior high school learners' reading comprehension levels of subtitles in selected movies.

This design was used because it utilized a post-test-only design and correlated the results or data gathered. This design, as aligned with the problem statements, did not need to be pre-tested. Also, this design uses and compares numerical or statistical data, including measuring the variables and analyzing the relationships between dependent, independent, and controlled variables to reveal the significance of correlations, comparisons, patterns, and causal relationships.

Respondents

The study's respondents were Grade 11 Senior High School learners for School Year 2022-2023. The Learner Information System (LIS) of the Department of Education officially has 189 learners for School Year 2022-2023, which were divided into four strands: General Academic Strand (GAS), Accountancy Business and Management (ABM), and Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) in the academic track with Home Economics in Technical Vocational and Livelihood Education (TVL). From these classes, Humanities and Social Sciences (48 Senior High School learners) and GAS (11 Senior High School learners) were purposively chosen since the Humanities and Social Sciences and General Academic Strand curriculum of the school offers creative writing in the first semester as an applied subject, which is not given in other strands.

The Humanities and Social Sciences and General Academic Strand learners were purposively sampled from the 189 Grade 11 Senior High School learners of the whole population of academic strands with the subject of Creative Writing. According to Dudovskiy (2022), purposive sampling is a non-probability method. Purposive sampling occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen by the believed sound and fair judgment of the researcher. It proves to be effective when limited numbers of people can serve as primary data sources of the research due to the nature of research design and research study objectives, which is the case of the current study stating that the primary and sole criteria in choosing the learners were that "they are officially enrolled in the subject Creative Writing for the School Year 2022-2023". It is shown in the table below.

<i>Classes / Strands</i>	<i>No. of Population</i>	<i>No. of Sample</i>
HUMSS	48	48
GAS	11	11
ABM	35	0
TVL	95	0
Total	189	59

The table shows the sample of Grade 11 learners as participants in the study. It can be seen that from the 189 learners in Grade 11, there were 48 enrolled in Humanities and Social Science (HUMSS), 11 in General Academic Strand (GAS), 35 in Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), and 95 in Technical-Vocational and Livelihood Education – Home Economics (TVL-HE). With these, only 59 were purposively selected since only 59 learners from HUMSS and GAS have the subject “Creative Writing” offered as part of their specialized subjects.

Instruments

The researcher used a self-devised test questionnaire in printed form to gather data from the respondents. This questionnaire was validated by 3 Master Teachers in English with master's and Doctoral Degrees in English for reliability and validity.

The instrument was reviewed by a panel of three experts in the field to establish content validity, as mentioned above. They examined the items' relevance, clarity, and representativeness of the measured construct. Based on their feedback, minor revisions were made to ensure the instrument's content validity. Kuder Richardson was utilized in a 20-item Multiple choice test with 28 participants for the reliability test since it tests only between right or wrong answers in this study instrument for multiple choice and score systems. The analysis revealed promising results for the internal consistency of the 20-item multiple-choice test. The proportion of agreement (p) for each item ranged from 0.64 to 0.93, indicating a high level of agreement among the participants. The computed variances of the proportion of agreement [$(\text{Var}(p))$] ranged from 0.062 to 0.025, suggesting relatively low variability in participant responses for each item. The total variance [$(\text{Var}(T))$] of the test was 8.77, indicating high variability across the entire test. Based on these calculations, the KR-20 coefficient was computed as 0.709, signifying a high level of internal consistency for the 20-item multiple-choice test.

The questionnaire was crafted around the statements of the problem, which included a 20-item post-test-only design in reading comprehension on the subtitles in movies, which was placed in order of comprehension level anchored with Barrett's Taxonomy of Reading Comprehension. Specifically, each level had four questions: literal comprehension, reorganization comprehension, evaluation comprehension, inferential comprehension, and appreciation comprehension.

The questionnaire is crafted with the Table of Test Specifications, creating a systematic approach for distributing items across various comprehension levels, namely literal comprehension, reorganization comprehension, inferential comprehension, evaluation comprehension, and appreciation comprehension. The Table of Test Specifications, uniquely developed for this study, is a researcher-made tool. It encompasses levels, objectives, hours/days taught, number of questions, percentage allocation, and item placement. The design of the Table of Test Specifications is specifically tailored to align with Barrett's Taxonomy of Reading Comprehension pertinent to this study, ensuring a comprehensive and targeted evaluation of the participants' comprehension skills in the specified areas from literal to appreciation comprehension.

Pilot testing for the study was conducted with Grade 11 GAS (General Academic Strand) learners from another senior high school in the district, with 28 learners pursuing creative writing with the aid of their respective subject teachers. Using a post-test design, the researcher gathered data on the learners' scores and performance during this period. After completing the pilot study, the researcher analyzed the data and determined the material and instrument on the learners' reading comprehension of movie subtitles. It was determined that the data collection procedures effectively obtained the pertinent data.

The researcher also collected feedback from the learners and teachers who participated in the pilot study to identify any issues or problems that required attention. Before conducting the main study, the researcher modified the research instruments' rubrics and implementation based on the pilot study results and feedback. It ensured the validity and dependability of the current study's findings and increased the likelihood of gaining meaningful insights from the research.

Procedure

This study followed a series of steps to the facilitated gathering of data and analysis of the results about the utilization of movie subtitles on the reading comprehension level of Senior High School learners in movies with subtitles that included the following:

The researcher prepared validated questionnaires for the post-test of movie subtitles in comprehension skills. The second step was utilizing the movie subtitles in film and video clip shows, titled "The Hunger Games – Book 1 to the Learners. "The Hunger Games" is a young adult dystopian novel by Suzanne Collins. It was first published in 2008 and was the first installment in "The Hunger Games" trilogy. The movie is set in a post-apocalyptic future, and the novel follows the story of Katniss Ever. The movie presents a sixteen-year-old girl who becomes a participant in the brutal Hunger Games. In this televised event, children fight to the death.

Following Film Education Framework (2023), the selected movie adhered to Film selection criteria such as the provision of good experiences and challenges, should be at the eye level of the participants or learners, education-relevant themes and content, enough length, can be in any category of genre, shows the culture and geographical diversity, and can be used for shared experiences and reflection.

The third step was conducting the test on the population of Senior High School learners taking "Creative Writing" during class hours as permitted by the school head, and it was collected immediately on the same day. It was followed by the analysis of the data and test of significant relationships using SPSS after the normality and homogeneity test to identify the parametric and non-parametric tests. The final step was the development of the study output, which is the informational material in the classification of the comprehension level of Senior High School learners in reading subtitles of selected movies.

Data Analysis

This part shows the statistical treatment applied in this research in interpreting the data, which included frequency-percentage distribution, percentage rating, and the non-parametric statistical tools Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis.

For sub-problem no.1, which dealt with the post-test in reading comprehension on the subtitles in movies skills, the percentage was used with the following formula: $P = (FS / N) \times 100$

Where: P = Percentage of Scores
FS = Frequency of Correct Responses
N = No. of Items

The computed percentage in the post-test shall be rated as follows:

<i>Percentage Range</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
90- 100	Outstanding
85-89	Very Satisfactory
80-84	Satisfactory
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations

This table showing the computed percent in the post-test was adopted from DepEd Order No. 8, S. 2015, also known as "Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program". It is generally followed nationwide in public and private schools in line with implementing the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533). It remained a standard guideline in all schools in assessment reporting, making it a valid and reliable scale for presenting and reporting the study results.

The Test of Normality was used to come up with a test for finding out the significant relationship using the SPSS tool for sub-problem number two, which deals with the significant relationship in the comprehension level of Senior High School learners.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that all the information gathered was treated with high confidentiality and used for academic purposes only in this study. Also, considering the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher used a consent letter and form to ascertain that all study respondents were willing to participate, as also approved by the parents. Before the study, letters were sent to the school principals and

parents for approval. When permission was granted to the researcher, an orientation was conducted for the respondents and parents, where the researchers explained the salient points of the study to include the respondents' rights and privileges if they participated in this research. They were also asked to sign the informed consent form, which signified their voluntary participation. The respondents' and the schools' identities were kept confidential.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the study findings following the sequenced statements of the problem. Data were presented using tabular with narrative text, analysis and interpretation, and implications.

Reading Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners After Using Movie Subtitles

Table 1. *Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners in Reading Subtitles on Selected Movies in Terms of Literal Comprehension*

<i>Literal Level Items</i>	<i>Frequency (N)</i>	<i>Percentage of Learners by Comprehension Level</i>	<i>Qualitative Index by Individual Learner</i>
90%-100%	53	89.83	O
85%-89%	6	10.17	VS
80%-84%	0	0	-
75%-79%	0	0	-
Total	59	100	

Legend: 90% - 100% - Outstanding (O), 85% - 89% - Very Satisfactory (VS), 80% - 84% - Satisfactory (S), 75% - 79% - Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

Table 1 presents the reading comprehension level of senior high school learners after using movie subtitles regarding literal comprehension. It reveals that of the 59 learners, 53, or 89.83 percent, reached a reading comprehension level with a qualitative index of Outstanding. Six or 10.17 percent was in the qualitative index of Very Satisfactory.

The fact that 89.83 percent of learners attained an exceptional reading comprehension level suggests that subtitles enhanced their ability to comprehend and interpret the literal information presented in the film. The remaining 10.17 percent of learners attained a Very Satisfactory level, indicating they still had a high level of comprehension. In addition, when computed, the mean percentage score of 98.47 is interpreted as Outstanding, indicating that the pupils' overall performance was Outstanding. This result supports the conclusion that using movie subtitles can be an effective instructional tool for enhancing learners' literal comprehension.

With this, teachers may consider using movie subtitles as a teaching tool to enhance their learners' comprehension of literal information, as the statement implies. Subtitles can be an effective way for learners to comprehend and interpret the information presented in a film. It can be especially beneficial for learners who struggle with reading or auditory comprehension and those with diverse language skills. In addition to other instructional strategies, teachers may incorporate movie subtitles into their lesson plans. Doing so can provide a more engaging and diverse learning environment for their learners, improving information retention.

Also, it further implies that learners could improve their comprehension of literal information by utilizing movie subtitles. Learners can benefit from the visual and auditory stimulation provided by the film while reading the subtitles, which gives additional support to comprehending the material. In addition, the study's findings suggest that learners who use movie subtitles may achieve a higher level of comprehension, which can contribute to improved academic performance. Therefore, learners struggling with a particular subject or topic may consider using movie subtitles as a study aid.

These findings were also evident in the study of Isidor (2015), emphasizing that learners at the literal level can recognize the information given. They must be able to recall or verify details, the primary data in the characters or events, the sequence of the things that happened, and simple comparison and contrast or even common relationships in the story that a high school learner must do effectively. It is supported by the Described and Captioned Media Program (2022) noting that learners should be way higher already than the literal ideas presented in the text and that it must already be an easy task. However, only some who are challenged have strong language backgrounds. With this, Benecio (2020) cited that movie subtitles help learners focus on learning the visual aside from the aural language inputs, making it easy to process and remember.

On the other hand, Chan (2022) pointed out in the study that though the literal or literal appreciation of the events, characters, and places is done by the learners through the use of subtitles, it must also be clearly stated in the plans and assessments of the teachers for the class in the day that further maximizes the use of movie subtitles through relevant activities. Also, Pujadas and Muñoz (2018) emphasize that subtitles' quality affects the learners' literal memory; in contrast, the better the quality, the higher the learners' on-screen text support and retention, engaging even the weakest learners.

Table 2 illustrates the reading comprehension level of senior high school learners after using movie subtitles regarding reorganization comprehension. It reveals that of 59 learners, 49 or 83.05 percent reached a reading comprehension level with a qualitative index of Outstanding. Ten or 16.95 percent was in the qualitative index of Very Satisfactory.

Table 2. *Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners in Reading Subtitles on Selected Movies in Terms of Reorganization Comprehension*

<i>Literal Level Items</i>	<i>Frequency (N)</i>	<i>Percentage of Learners by Comprehension Level</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation by Individual Learner</i>
90%-100%	49	83.05	O
85%-89%	10	16.95	VS
80%-84%	0	0	-
75%-79%	0	0	-
Total	59	100	

Legend: 90% - 100% - Outstanding (O), 85% - 89% - Very Satisfactory (VS), 80% - 84% - Satisfactory (S), 75% - 79% - Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

With these findings, it could be put forward that the use of movie subtitles improved learners' capacity to understand the structure and organization of the information offered in the film, as evidenced by the fact that 83.05 percent of learners achieved an Outstanding level of reading comprehension in terms of reorganization comprehension. Ten percent of learners scored very satisfactorily, indicating they retained high comprehension. Furthermore, when computed, the mean percentage score of 97.46 percent is considered excellent, supporting the conclusion that using movie subtitles can help improve learners' reorganization comprehension.

Teachers should consider using movie subtitles as a teaching tool to help their learners understand the structure and organization of the material delivered in a film. It is beneficial for kids who need help with organization and information flow. Teachers can provide a more diversified and engaging learning environment by incorporating movie subtitles into their lesson plans, resulting in higher information retention.

Movie subtitles can also help learners enhance their reorganization comprehension of literal content. Learners who need help understanding the order and flow of material may benefit from using movie subtitles. According to the study's findings, kids who watch movies with subtitles may attain a higher level of comprehension, which can lead to increased academic achievement. As a result, learners having difficulty grasping the structure and organization of literal information may benefit from employing movie subtitles as a study tool.

It is similarly evident in the study of Isidor (2015) that the learners are expected to read between the lines from their schemata or prior learning and stock knowledge on the topics being discussed. It was also suggested that learners must be able to think and search for a clause in the text and appreciate the context and contents presented for the deeper meaning of the structures of the story or narratives. Also, Hall and Barnes (2017) cited in a study that the hat comprehension skills of the learners are improved through activities and materials that trigger their inference thinking from background knowledge, such as the use of moving text or subtitles. Likewise, Han et al. (2019) emphasizes that movie subtitles, like digital text or moving text, draw the learners' attention and make them focused readers and viewers, enabling them to remember the core ideas of the material being viewed. The subtitles create visual and literal prompts that lead to inferential thinking in many parts of the movie. Lastly, McMaster et al. (2014) assert that comprehension of the materials viewed in films or videos is multi-dimensional, which helps create a coherent mental representation of the story. With this, decoding of the ideas and experiences integration is facilitated through active thinking of the learners because movie subtitles act as triggers and signs for language event awareness.

Table 3. *Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners in Reading Subtitles on Selected Movies in Terms of Inferential Comprehension*

<i>Literal Level Items</i>	<i>Frequency (N)</i>	<i>Percentage of Learners by Comprehension Level</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation by Individual Learner</i>
90%-100%	50	84.75	O
85%-89%	9	15.25	VS
80%-84%	0	0	-
75%-79%	0	0	-
Total	59	100	

Legend: 90% - 100% - Outstanding (O), 85% - 89% - Very Satisfactory (VS), 80% - 84% - Satisfactory (S), 75% - 79% - Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

Table 3 demonstrates the reading comprehension level of the senior high school learners after using movie subtitles regarding inferential comprehension. It was made known that from the 59 learners, 50 or 84.75 percent of the sample attained a reading comprehension level under a qualitative index of Outstanding. Nine or 15.95 percent was in the qualitative index of Very Satisfactory.

These findings indicate that movie subtitles can improve senior high school learners' inferential comprehension of literal information. The data shows that 84.75 percent of the learners achieved an Outstanding level of comprehension, while 15.95 percent achieved a Very Satisfactory level. This result suggests that using movie subtitles can be an effective tool for enhancing learners' inferential comprehension. Utilizing movie subtitles improves the learners' inferential comprehension of literal information. By using movie subtitles, they can benefit from both the visual and auditory cues presented in the film while also being able to read the subtitles for additional support in understanding the reasoning behind the information presented.

Also, it implied further that for teachers, incorporating movie subtitles into their lesson plans can be an effective instructional strategy to enhance learners' inferential comprehension. It can be constructive for learners who need help understanding the reasoning behind

the information presented. By using movie subtitles, teachers can provide a more varied and engaging learning experience for their learners, leading to better retention of information and improved academic performance.

These study results are supported by researchers stating that appreciating literature, watching movies with subtitles, and engaging in other learning activities require critical, analytical, and interpretive skills through inferential comprehension. McCarthy (2015) emphasized that comprehension of text and literature, even in movies, requires understanding the literal and nonliteral meaning of the text. However, the psychological processes in constructing interpretations still need to be fully understood. Similarly, watching movies with subtitles involves interpreting nonverbal cues, symbolism, and subtext, which requires engagement in the process of interpretation to construct a deeper understanding of the movie's meaning. Critical comprehension, analytical comprehension, and interpretive comprehension are essential skills for effective communication, problem-solving, and decision-making in a variety of contexts under inferential comprehension, as highlighted by Moghadam et al. (2021), Murphy et al. (2016), and Ahmad and Siddiqui (2021). Inferential comprehension involves critical comprehension that requires actively engaging with a text to analyze and evaluate its ideas and arguments.

In contrast, analytical comprehension involves breaking down complex information into its parts and drawing logical conclusions based on that examination. Interpretive comprehension, conversely, consists of understanding a text's literal meaning and going beyond it to uncover deeper layers of meaning. These comprehension skills equip learners with the ability to reflect on their own experiences and perspectives and engage with the world around them in a more meaningful way. Lastly, Liao (2020) asserted that movie subtitles help learners improve their understanding of the words, exposure to the actual use of the words, and the suprasegmental factors of the language, as seen in the videos. With these, learners are directed to facilitate literal, critical, analytical, or holistic inferential comprehension in making correct propositions and judgments.

Table 4. *Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners in Reading Subtitles on Selected Movies in Terms of Evaluation Comprehension*

<i>Literal Level Items</i>	<i>Frequency (N)</i>	<i>Percentage of Learners by Comprehension Level</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation by Individual Learner</i>
90%-100%	53	89.83	O
85%-89%	6	10.17	VS
80%-84%	0	0	-
75%-79%	0	0	-
Total	59	100	

Legend: 90% - 100% - Outstanding (O), 85% - 89% - Very Satisfactory (VS), 80% - 84% - Satisfactory (S), 75% - 79% - Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

Table 4 demonstrates the evaluation comprehension level of the senior high school learners' reading comprehension after using movie subtitles. It reveals that 53 learners, or 89.83 percent of the total sample of 59, achieved a reading comprehension level under an Outstanding qualitative index. Six or 10.17 percent, were ranked Very Satisfactory quality index.

These findings prove that movie subtitles can effectively aid senior high school learners' evaluation comprehension of literal information in English or English-medium subjects. The data reveals that 89.83 percent of the 59 learners obtained exceptional reading comprehension, while 10.17 percent achieved a high-performance level. In addition, as computed, the mean percentage score of 98.47 is interpreted as exceptional, providing further evidence that using movie subtitles can enhance learners' evaluation of subject comprehension.

It implies the lens of teachers that should consider using movie subtitles as a teaching instrument to improve their learners' evaluation comprehension of literal information. By incorporating movie subtitles into their lesson plans, teachers can provide learners with a more engaging and diverse learning environment, improving information retention. Also, it suggested to learners that using movie subtitles can be a valuable aid for improving their evaluation comprehension of literal information when viewing videos. Table 4's positive results suggest that learners who use movie subtitles may attain a higher level of comprehension than those who do not, leading to improved performance output, written or spoken, as a result of greater comprehension. Learners can also discover strategies to aid their language learning and reviews.

In a similar study, evaluation comprehension is a complex process that involves a range of cognitive and affective processes, such as inference-making, critical thinking, and metacognition as to evaluative thinking of the materials. According to Van Renswoude (2022), evaluation comprehension is a critical aspect of reading comprehension that involves the reader's ability to evaluate and judge the text's content, quality, and credibility in many aspects, even in videos and movies. In evaluation comprehension, learners can do critical thinking, which is a crucial component in understanding and involves the learners' ability to analyze and evaluate the arguments, evidence, and assumptions presented in the text or movie subtitles (Ennis, 2018).

Metacognition is also an essential aspect of evaluation comprehension that is done by the learners to effectively comprehend the material, as it allows the reader to monitor their understanding of the text, identify areas of confusion, and adjust their reading strategies according to (Babashamasi et al., 2019). Inference-making is also closely related to assessing comprehension, as it allows the viewers and readers to go beyond the surface-level information presented in the text and make judgments based on their background knowledge and experiences (Lopez, 2022), as it is applied in movie subtitles. Explicit instruction and practice in these strategies can improve

learners' evaluation comprehension skills, and it is vital in the age of digital media, where the credibility and reliability of information can be blurred but are explicitly shown in the movie subtitles.

Likewise, movie subtitles can facilitate learners' learning comprehension, cognitive load, and satisfaction when generated according to learner needs and chosen activity presented in a way readily appreciated (Malakul & Park, 2023). Also, subtitles improve comprehension, and subtitles can be used to support learners in an authentic academic context, particularly in English-medium instruction where English is not their first language (Chan & Kruger, 2022). Integrated subtitles did not benefit children's reading patterns, scene recognition performance, or comprehension of the clips (Black, 2022).

Lastly, according to Napikul et al. (2018), subtitles do improve the comprehension and vocabulary of the learners' facilitated evaluation comprehension of the story's public events from low-level to higher-level understanding, especially if the chosen subtitles are those that are commonly used by the learners both in local or English language.

Table 5. *Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners in Reading Subtitles on Selected Movies in Terms of Appreciation Comprehension*

<i>Literal Level Items</i>	<i>Frequency (N)</i>	<i>Percentage of Learners by Comprehension Level</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation by Individual Learner</i>
90%-100%	59	100	O
85%-89%	0	0	-
80%-84%	0	0	-
75%-79%	0	0	-
Total	59	100	

Legend: 90% - 100% - Outstanding (O), 85% - 89% - Very Satisfactory (VS), 80% - 84% - Satisfactory (S), 75% - 79% - Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

Table 5 shows the appreciation comprehension level of the senior high school learners' reading comprehension after using movie subtitles. It reveals that all 59 or 100 percent of learner samples achieved a reading comprehension level under an Outstanding qualitative index. The Senior High School participants scored 3.25 to 4 out of four items in the comprehension level.

Learners can benefit significantly from using movie subtitles to better learn and recall complicated written content, as shown by the favorable results in the table. It can be helpful for learners who have trouble reading or speaking various languages. The outcomes also suggest that employing movie subtitles as a teaching tool can make classrooms more welcoming and accessible to learners of all backgrounds. Teachers can better accommodate learners with diverse language skills and those with trouble with auditory or visual processing by using movie subtitles in their lesson plans.

For teachers, movie subtitles can effectively improve learners' appreciation of comprehension of literal content. Learners whose native language is not English or who have other language barriers may benefit significantly from this. Teachers can give their pupils an excellent tool for comprehending and remembering complex literal material by having them watch movies with subtitles. The conclusion for learners is that increased value-added comprehension of literal information gained from movie subtitles can enhance academic achievement. Table 5's encouraging findings provide hope that learners who employ this method will show improvement in their understanding and performance in class.

As evident also in the study of Pinoliad (2021), learners in the appreciation comprehension can use decoding systems they devise themselves, language and background experience into play as they analyze, synthesize, and evaluate contents at the highest level. From this point, they can show relevance and credibility to what they have viewed or read. Likewise, Gonzales (2020) also mentioned that with subtitles and electronic presentations like games, subtitles play an essential part in helping viewers and readers metacognitively process the information in their minds. There were various ways for the learners to interpret and appreciate the text and the images, even across varied life contexts.

McKeown and Curtis (2016) cited that with appreciation comprehension and teacher strategies, learners could move far beyond the surface level and critically appreciate the text as applied in creating or doing things in action. Lastly, Wang and Hermans (2016) also noted that emotions and knowledge interplay in appreciation comprehension by applying what is learned and responding from their lens.

Lastly, Chan and Kruger (2022) support these findings by citing that subtitles do create an academic and lifelike context in which the words and language as a medium of learning are practiced become integrated into the conscious and subconscious constructs of the learners, making them creative and authentic thinker for new ideas to apply what has been comprehended.

Table 6 presents a detailed summary of the reading comprehension level of the senior high school learners after using movie subtitles in the subject of Creative Writing. It demonstrates that the 59 learner participants in the study attained a reading comprehension level from Very Satisfactory to Outstanding, with the majority at the Outstanding level. Specifically, literal has 53 (89.83 percent) Outstanding and six (10.17 percent) Very Satisfactory; reorganization has 49 (83.05 percent) Outstanding and ten (16.95 percent) Very Satisfactory; inferential has 50 (84.75 percent) Outstanding and nine (15.25 percent) Very Satisfactory; evaluation has 53 (89.83 percent) Outstanding and six (10.17 percent) Very Satisfactory; and appreciation has 59 (100 percent) Outstanding. From these five reading comprehension levels, the highest scores were in the appreciation level, while the lowest was in the reorganization level.

However, both levels attained a higher percentage of learners.

Table 6. Detailed Summary of Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners in Reading Subtitles on Selected Movies by Sample and Percentage

Comprehension Level	Reading comprehension Level									
	Literal		Reorganization		Inferential		Evaluation		Appreciation	
	N	P	N	P	N	P	N	P	N	P
Outstanding	53	89.83	49	83.05	50	84.75	53	89.83	59	100
Very Satisfactory	6	10.17	10	16.95	9	15.25	6	10.17	0	0
Satisfactory	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fairly Satisfactory	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	59	100	59	100	59	100	59	100	59	100

Legend: 90% - 100% - Outstanding (O), 85% - 89% - Very Satisfactory (VS), 80% - 84% - Satisfactory (S), 75% - 79% - Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

Since the study found that the majority of the learners achieved either a Very Satisfactory or Outstanding level of comprehension in all five categories: literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation, and appreciation its findings are far-reaching and can be relevant to various stakeholders, such as education, curriculum, instructional materials, teachers, and learners. The study's findings support the idea that using subtitles in the classroom can help pupils learn far more from movies. Teachers who care about their pupils' academic progress may find this finding significant. Reading comprehension is crucial to learning across disciplines, giving them a possible answer for those struggling. Based on the findings, teachers may incorporate movie subtitles to boost learners' comprehension skills across disciplines. As a result of this discovery, educators will be better able to create a curriculum that meets the needs of pupils with a wide range of learning preferences.

Moreover, the study results indicate that movie subtitles can effectively teach viewers how to understand what they see. Educators can use this data to design engaging and practical lessons that help pupils strengthen their reading comprehension. In turn, this can enrich pupils' educational opportunities. There are ramifications for educators based on the study's findings as well. The research emphasizes the value of testing learners' knowledge in various domains to pinpoint problem areas. As a result, educators will be better able to tailor their lessons to the specific needs of their learners. Finally, the research demonstrates that learners can benefit from employing movie subtitles to increase their reading comprehension in a fun and practical way. Need interest-based facilitation of learning can boost learner motivation and improve learning outcomes, which are critical to the learners' academic performance.

The findings are supported by Negi and Mitra (2022) and Garcia (2017), who found out that with movie subtitles, learners can low to high-level cognitive capacities or thinking processes that match the learners' needs in listening and reading into viewing and so they can think highly effective in any level of comprehension from literal to appreciation. Also, Liao (2020) emphasized that movie subtitles act as language-learning tools in communicative activities where the learners' focus is given, and they learn from the vocabulary and the context provided.

Furthermore, Cojean and Martin (2021) emphasized that learning the story and content is facilitated in movies with subtitles due to thinking and processing that are made accessible to remember and comprehend with the vocabulary and context of the scenes or elements of the story in actual play.

Generally, the study suggests that incorporating movie subtitles can effectively enhance reading comprehension levels, leading to better learning outcomes for learners. The findings can inform the development of more innovative curricula, teaching methods, and instructional materials that cater to the diverse needs of learners. It can also motivate teachers to provide targeted support for learners who need it, leading to a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

Table 7. Summary of Reading Comprehension Level on the Senior High School Learners After Using Movie Subtitles

Category	Percentage Rating	Qualitative Index
A. Literal	98.47	Outstanding
B. Reorganization	97.46	Outstanding
C. Inferential	97.71	Outstanding
D. Evaluation	98.47	Outstanding
F. Appreciation	98.79	Outstanding
Total	98.18	Outstanding

Legend: 90% - 100% - Outstanding (O), 85% - 89% - Very Satisfactory (VS), 80% - 84% - Satisfactory (S), 75% - 79% - Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

Table 7 shows the summary of the reading comprehension level of the senior high school learners after using movie subtitles in percentage rating by level. It demonstrates that all the comprehension levels have a percentage rating of 97 percent and above, described in a qualitative index as Outstanding specifically, from the highest percentage, appreciation (98.79 percent), literal and reorganization (98.47 percent), inferential (98.71 percent), and reorganization (97.46 percent). It presents further that the highest percentage was appreciation while the lowest was reorganization, though both were described Outstandingly in the qualitative index. Senior high school learners have Outstanding comprehension performance in all categories of comprehension after using movie subtitles.

These findings implied that using movie subtitles can help learners in literal comprehension, where they can understand the literal meaning of a text in the movie. It involves identifying and comprehending the main ideas, details, and facts presented in the movie. Reorganization comprehension can facilitate learners' understanding of how a text is organized and structured. It involves recognizing the different components of a text, such as the introduction, body, and conclusion, and how they are connected coherently while also being able to organize their ideas and make inferences about the events.

Learners can also do reason comprehension to understand and analyze the logical arguments presented in a movie and text. It involves identifying the author's claims, evidence, and reasoning and evaluating their validity and soundness. They also succeed in assessing comprehension so they can evaluate the effectiveness of one's comprehension strategies and adjust as needed. It involves monitoring one's understanding while reading or listening and making necessary adjustments to improve comprehension. Lastly, they can do a higher level of appreciation comprehension to appreciate and critically evaluate the content and ideas presented in a text. It involves considering the text's relevance, significance, and implications for oneself and others by creating and applying what is learned through the movie subtitles.

Also, it provides a possible teaching strategy for teachers to enhance their pupils' comprehension abilities. They can include the usage of movie subtitles in their lesson plans because it can improve learner comprehension and help them better understand the material. Additionally, they can differentiate education for pupils with varying levels of language competency using this strategy. It offers advice on improving pupils' comprehension abilities in many areas. Learners' capacity to comprehend a text's literal meaning, recognize its structure, examine logical arguments, assess their comprehension tactics, and appreciate a text's content can all be improved by using movie subtitles.

Additionally, this strategy offers a fun and exciting way to learn. It also implies that multimedia resources can be used in the classroom to improve learners' understanding abilities. It also emphasizes using various representational techniques, such as videos with subtitles in training, to cater to learners' demands.

The findings are supported by Supangesti et al. (2018), who found that movie subtitles give life to the written language through reading subtitles of movies and give these languages a higher chance to be memorized and interpreted creatively by the learners. Also, Negi and Mitra (2022) and Garcia (2017) discovered that with movie subtitles, learners could use low to high-level cognitive capacities or thinking processes that match the learners' needs reading subtitles of movies so they can think highly effectively at any level of comprehension from literal to appreciation. The researchers found that learners could use low to high-level cognitive capacities or thinking processes that matched the learners' needs in listening and reading into viewing. Liao (2020) also underlined movie subtitles' role as language learning aids in communicative activities.

Significant Relationship in the Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners after Using Movie Subtitles

Table 8. *Test of Normality of the Reading Comprehension Level of Senior High School Learners After Using Movie Subtitles*

Category	Test of Normality Result	Statistical Tool
A. Literal	Not Normal	Non-Parametric (Spearman's rho)
B. Reorganization	Not Normal	Non-Parametric (Spearman's rho)
C. Inferential	Not Normal	Non-Parametric (Spearman's rho)
D. Evaluation	Not Normal	Non-Parametric (Spearman's rho)
F. Appreciation	Not Normal	Non-Parametric (Spearman's rho)

Table 8 presents the normality test results for senior high school learners' reading comprehension levels after exposure to movie subtitles. The findings indicate a "Not Normal" classification for all categories, suggesting skewed data, outliers, or non-compliance with normal distribution assumptions. Consequently, the analysis implemented a non-parametric tool, specifically Spearman's rho correlation coefficient, to examine relationships among literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation, and appreciation comprehension levels. This approach is suitable for variables that do not follow a typical distribution.

Table 9 illustrates Spearman's rho test result in finding the relationship in the reading comprehension level of the senior high school learners after using movie subtitles. It shows that the reading comprehension level of literal has a very weak or negative correlation with reorganization through $r(59)=-0.152$ and $p=0.250>0.05$; weak correlation with inferential through $r(59)=-0.013$ and $p=0.921>0.05$; weak correlation with evaluation though $r(59)=-0.072$ and $p=0.586>0.05$; and weak correlation with appreciation though $r(59)=-0.048$ and $p=0.720>0.05$ which all failed to reject the H_0 and not a significant relationship.

The reorganization has a weak correlation with inferential through $r(59)=-0.060$ and $p=0.654>0.05$; a weak correlation with evaluation through $r(59)=-0.147$ and $p=0.267>0.05$; and a weak correlation with appreciation though $r(59)=-0.077$ and $p=0.563>0.05$ which all failed to reject the H_0 and not a significant relationship. Inferential has a weak correlation with evaluation though $r(59)=-0.013$ and $p=0.921>0.05$ and very weak or negative correlation with appreciation though $r(59)=-0.049$ and $p=-0.714>0.05$, which all failed to reject the H_0 and not a significant relationship.

Table 9. *Spearman's Rho Test Result in Finding the Relationship in the Reading Comprehension Levels of Senior High School Learners After Using Movie Subtitles*

<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>rho value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>The impression at 0.05 level of significance</i>		
Literal	Reorganization	59	98.47	-0.152	0.25	Failed to	Not Significant		
				Very Weak		Reject Ho			
	0.013			0.92	Failed to	Not Significant			
	Weak				Reject Ho				
Evaluation	Appreciation	59	98.47	0.072	0.59	Failed to	Not Significant		
				Weak		Reject Ho			
0.048	0.72			Failed to	Not Significant				
Weak				Reject Ho					
Reorganization	Inferential	59	97.46	0.060	0.65	Failed to	Not Significant		
				Weak		Reject Ho			
	0.147			0.27	Failed to	Not Significant			
	Weak				Reject Ho				
Appreciation	Inferential	59	97.71	0.077	0.56	Failed to	Not Significant		
				Weak		Reject Ho			
0.013	0.92			Failed to	Not Significant				
Weak				Reject Ho					
Inferential	Appreciation	59	97.71	0.049	0.71	Failed to	Not Significant		
				Very Weak		Reject Ho			
Evaluation	Appreciation			59	98.47	-0.064	0.63	Failed to	Not Significant
						Very Weak		Reject Ho	
						Correlation			

Evaluation has a very weak or negative correlation with appreciation though $r(59) = -0.064$ and $p = 0.629 > 0.05$, which also failed to reject the H_0 and showed no significant relationship. Appreciation, as shown in another comprehension level, also shows $r(59) = -0.064$ to 0.077 with very weak or negative to weak correlation and $p = 0.563$ to 0.720 , which also failed to reject H_0 and arrived at the impression of insignificant. Generally, the decisions failed to reject the null hypothesis in all the comprehension levels, and the impression needed to be more significant. With this, there is no significant relationship in the comprehension level of the Senior High School learners after using movie subtitles.

The findings imply that reorganization scores tend to decrease as literal scores increase, but this relationship is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant. It also suggests that there may be some weak relationships between inferential, reorganization, and Literary variables, but they are not strong enough to be considered statistically significant. The same is the case with evaluation, reorganization, and Literary variables. Lastly, appreciation is not significantly correlated with other variables, suggesting no evidence of a significant relationship between appreciation and any other variables in the sample. These findings suggest very weak to negative and non-significant correlations among the variables. However, it is essential to note that the sample size is relatively small ($N = 59$), which may have limited the ability to detect significant correlations that can also be considered for future studies.

These findings did not concur with the study of Hosseini et al. (2012), stating that there is a positive relationship between comprehension level and strategies for improving comprehension in EFL readers, though they are applied in reading. It similarly disagrees with Srisang and Everatt (2021), noting that lower and higher-level comprehension skills correlate significantly. However, Hamouda and Tarlochan (2015) emphasize that levels of comprehension are connected since the lowest levels of literal, reorganization, inferential, and evaluation are spirally increasing in difficulty. They must be related, with the processes only increasing and integrating. On the other hand, Dizon and Thanyawatpokin (2021) assert from the study's findings that there is a tremendous increase in performance and assessment scores of the learners in comprehension when the material for instruction is in the form of movies or videos with subtitles.

The Classification of the Comprehension Level of SHS Learners in Reading Subtitles of Selected Movies

The comprehension level of Senior High School learners in reading subtitles of a selected movie (The Hunger Games – First Book) was verbally interpreted as Outstanding in all the classifications. It means that after the post-test has been given, the students have gained a 90 percent-100 percent average in the test for all reading comprehension levels following Barrett's taxonomy. From these, it implied that reading selected movie subtitles increases the students' performance and may give them focus, increased retention, understanding, and other higher-order thinking skills such as critical, creative, and analytical thinking. Thus, reading subtitles of

selected movies is beneficial and may be continued. Finally, the student's comprehension levels are Outstanding in the classifications such as the following:

1. Literal comprehension is understanding a given viewed text's figurative and literal meaning. It entails recognizing and comprehending a readable text's primary concepts, specifics, and facts. It is being literal and knowledgeable about the subject matter and facts.
2. Reorganization comprehension refers to the order and construction of a viewed text. It refers to the ability to comprehend how a viewed text is organized and the significance of each arrangement or connection in the ideas. It entails differentiating the various components of a viewed text, such as the introduction, body, and conclusion, and how these components are related to one another through inferential understanding and reorganization of ideas and events.
3. Inferential comprehension is the ability to understand and critically evaluate the logical arguments presented in written material. It necessitates recognizing the author's claims, evidence, and reasoning and evaluating the validity and soundness of those claims, evidence, and reasoning. Inferential comprehension entails analyzing the viewed text, drawing inferences from the analysis, and performing interpretive and critical thinking with explanations beyond the text.
4. Evaluation Comprehension is the ability to evaluate the effectiveness of one's comprehension strategies and adjust as needed. It is the ability to check one's comprehension while watching and make necessary adjustments to improve one's comprehension. It is the understanding evaluation aspect by which the learner's comprehension is measured. It involves assessing the credibility and dependability of the story, its quality, the effectiveness of the visuals and audio, the various perspectives on the events, and drawing conclusions based on the story's specific and holistic direction.
5. Appreciation comprehension is enjoying and critically analyzing the information and ideas presented in a viewed text. This ability is known as "valuable comprehension." It entails considering the applicability, significance, and implications of the viewed text for oneself and others in the context of the discussion. It is where learners identify key themes and ideas, describe the language and imagery completely, make connections to personal experiences, evaluate the impact of the content, and appreciate the aesthetic qualities of the video through something created as an output with performance or a project.

Output of the Study: Developed Informational Material for Senior High School Learner's Reading Comprehension Level of Subtitles in Selected Movies

The study's findings reveal weak or very weak correlations among different comprehension levels of Senior High School learners after utilizing movie subtitles. Literal comprehension shows a very weak, negative correlation with reorganization, inferential, evaluation, and appreciation, all of which fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and indicate no significant relationship. Reorganization exhibits weak correlations with inferential, evaluation, and appreciation, all failing to reject H_0 . Inferential comprehension displays weak correlations with evaluation and appreciation, again failing to reject H_0 . Evaluation has a very weak correlation with appreciation, and both fail to show a significant relationship. Appreciation, across comprehension levels, demonstrates very weak to weak correlations with other variables, failing to reject H_0 .

These results imply that there is no significant relationship in the comprehension levels of senior high school learners after exposure to movie subtitles. The findings suggest potential trends, such as a decrease in reorganization scores with an increase in literal scores, but these trends lack statistical significance. The weak relationships among inferential, reorganization, and literary variables also do not reach statistical significance.

Thus, the crafting of the Informational Material output for Senior High School learners' reading comprehension level of subtitles in selected movies, anchored in Barrett's Taxonomy of Reading Comprehension, would be best suited for ladder acquisition from literal to appreciation comprehension. The findings indicate weak or very weak correlations among comprehension levels, emphasizing the need to structure the material in a sequential manner, starting with a focus on literal understanding and gradually progressing to appreciation, recognizing the non-significant relationships among these comprehension dimensions.

In developing the Information material, it used general domain theory (Schommer-Aikins & Duell, 2013). Domain general theory refers to theoretical frameworks that aim to explain cognitive processes or abilities applicable across different domains or areas of knowledge, that is, reading skills in the English language. This theory posits that specific cognitive processes or skills are not domain-specific but generalizable across multiple domains, notably English language macro skills. When developing information material for reading movie subtitles, domain-general theory can be a foundation for identifying and categorizing cognitive processes relevant to comprehension across various visual media.

Research results with concepts and theories in information material have been extensively developed to comprehend the cognitive processes involved in comprehending written text in the context of reading comprehension. The findings above emphasized decoding, vocabulary knowledge, drawing inferences, and text structure analysis when reading subtitles, which became the basis of information material for reading subtitles while considering the distinctive cognitive processes and skills required for comprehending visual media.

The domain-general theory of reading comprehension steps were taken to develop the information material in SHS learners' reading

comprehension on subtitles in selected movies.

Determine Frequent Cognitive Processes. Examine theories and taxonomies of reading comprehension to identify cognitive processes shared by reading and reading comprehension. These may include activating prior knowledge, drawing inferences, analyzing visual elements, interpreting symbols and cues, and integrating information.

Adapt Cognition to Visual Media. Consider the manifestations of these cognitive processes in the context of visual comprehension. Examine the impact of visual elements such as images, videos, graphs, and diagrams on the cognitive processes involved in comprehension. In place of decoding written text, for instance, visual comprehension may involve interpreting and analyzing the meaning conveyed by visual representations.

Create hierarchical tiers. Determine the taxonomic level of the reading comprehension hierarchy. From lower-level perceptual skills to higher-level integrative and evaluative processes, these levels may reflect the complexity of cognitive processes. Align these levels with the existing information material for reading subtitles or, if necessary, modify them to accommodate the distinctive characteristics of visual media.

Define Descriptive Statements. Create descriptors for each level of reading subtitles that outline the cognitive processes and skills necessary for reading comprehension. These statements should be observable and quantifiable, as required by the nature of visual media. A descriptive statement may involve recognizing and interpreting simple visual elements at the lower level, whereas, at the higher level, it may involve analyzing and synthesizing complex visual data.

Validate and Organize the Information in the Material. Organize the level and descriptive statements hierarchically to ensure a logical progression from simple to complex cognitive processes. Experts in visual comprehension or media studies should be consulted to validate the information material for reading subtitles and make necessary adjustments.

Using domain-general theory with the theories and taxonomies of reading comprehension, the researcher developed information material on reading comprehension that captures the cognitive processes and skills required to comprehend visual media or subtitles in a movie with Barrett Taxonomy. This information material for reading subtitles provided a framework for comprehending and evaluating learners' capacity to comprehend and interpret visual information, such as subtitled films.

This section presents the study's findings in the form of information material regarding the reading comprehension skills of learners when subtitled films are used in the classroom or a similar context involving subtitled videos.

Likewise, Scotto (2017) and Isidor (2015) cited that teachers need information material for learning to provide a structure for arranging and classifying learning aims and outcomes. The information material for reading in subtitles is a valuable tool for teachers because it allows them to classify learners' learning styles and determine the most appropriate methods of instruction and evaluation for each learner (Law Insider, 2023). An informational material of learning can also encourage a more organized strategy for education. Teachers can better organize their lessons and help learners retain information when they have a clear understanding of the various learning styles that are at play in the classroom. An information material provides a common language for describing learning objectives and outcomes, which can improve communication between teachers, learners, and other stakeholders. By doing so, we can better ensure that all parties involved in the educational process are on the same page regarding goals and progress.

Another study by Benecio (2020) found that with movie subtitles, learners' learning is maximized while making them think at a higher-order level. This study is due to the number of senses applied while viewing and reading simultaneously. Moreover, when appropriately guided with information material for reading subtitles of learning, learners' ability to process video inputs with relevant activities and support content learning would be highly improved to match the curriculum needs.

It was similarly supported in Barrett's taxonomy for reading subtitles of comprehension (1980), which asserts that learners move from the literal understanding to another until they fully understand and appreciate the cognitive and aesthetic aspects of the material in the highest hierarchy of comprehension.

From the results of this study, the learners' reading comprehension was tested after watching the subtitled movie, "The Hunger Games" first book.

The levels of comprehension are interrelated and build upon one another to develop a more holistic understanding of reading the subtitles of the movies, whereas:

Literal comprehension serves as the foundation of all other levels of comprehension as it involves grasping the literal and figurative meaning of the viewed text. With a basic understanding of the content and facts presented in the viewed text, it becomes easier to move on to higher levels of comprehension.

Reorganization comprehension builds upon literal comprehension by focusing on the organization and arrangement of ideas in the viewed text. Understanding the structure of the viewed text allows for a deeper understanding of how the author conveys their message and how different components of the viewed text are related.

Inferential comprehension further builds upon the previous levels of comprehension by requiring the viewer to analyze and critically

evaluate the logical arguments presented in the viewed text. It involves making inferences, interpreting the viewed text beyond the literal meaning, and evaluating the validity and soundness of the author's claims and evidence.

Evaluation comprehension goes beyond understanding the text's content by focusing on the viewer's comprehension strategies and evaluating their efficacy. This level of comprehension involves constantly monitoring one's understanding and making necessary adjustments to improve comprehension.

Appreciation comprehension involves appreciating and critically analyzing the material and ideas offered in a viewed text. This level of comprehension requires the viewer to identify key themes and ideas, make connections to personal experiences, and evaluate the impact of the content on themselves and others. It also involves creating an output, such as a project or performance, demonstrating one's understanding and appreciation of the text.

Overall, the different levels of comprehension are interdependent and serve as building blocks for developing a more comprehensive understanding of a viewed text. Each level contributes to a deeper understanding of the viewed text, and learners can improve their comprehension skills by engaging with the viewed text at each of these levels.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The integration of movie subtitles resulted in a notable increase in the comprehension levels of Senior High School learners, spanning literal, reorganization, inferential, evaluation, and appreciation comprehension, achieving an Outstanding qualitative index.

The study's findings reveal a significant improvement in the comprehension level of Senior High School learners following the utilization of movie subtitles, highlighting the positive impact of this multimedia resource on their reading comprehension skills.

Students demonstrated outstanding performance across all classifications of comprehension levels, showcasing the effectiveness of the selected movies and quality subtitles in facilitating their understanding of content and achieving high assessment results.

Based on the study's outcomes, it is concluded that crafting informational material for reading subtitles should focus on key concepts, principles, relationships among variables, applications, and limitations of comprehension levels. This material should incorporate relevant examples and educational use cases to enhance the learners' overall understanding.

Considering the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

For the Learners. Analyze the findings to understand how subtitled movies contribute to improved comprehension, allowing to identify specific areas of strength and weakness.

Apply the insights gained from the informational material by allowing for targeted interventions to address specific reading weaknesses, ensuring a more comprehensive and interconnected approach to learning. Participate actively in the development and utilization of informational material paired with video subtitles.

For the Language Teachers. Recognize how Senior High School learners navigate reading subtitles, enabling them to grasp the hints and challenges associated with this skill.

Implement strategies that cater to diverse learner needs, aiming for higher achievement outcomes in subjects where reading comprehension with subtitles is applicable. Analyze the study's findings to predict and facilitate planning and preparation for teaching activities.

For the Administrators. Assess the implications for educational policies, considering factors such as resource allocation, teacher training, and curriculum development. Collaborate with educators to design comprehensive strategies that address the identified needs of learners in subjects where reading comprehension with subtitles is applicable. Assess learner performance in subjects related to reading comprehension with subtitles, making data-driven adjustments as needed.

For the Future Researchers. Recognize the valid and tangible results provided by the current study on Senior High School learners' reading comprehension levels when utilizing subtitles. Use the information as a point of reference for designing studies, ensuring that methodologies, materials, instruments, and processes align with the proven effectiveness highlighted in the current research.

Share findings, methodologies, and insights to facilitate the growth of fellow researchers, contributing not only to personal and professional development but also to the collective advancement of research in the field.

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